

CORE BEHAVIORAL COMEPETENCIES AND TEACHERS' JOB SATISFACTION: BASIS FOR TEACHER COMPETENCY DEVELOPMENT PLAN

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ABSTRACT

The role of teachers' core behavioral competencies is fundamental in their performance, satisfaction and overall effectiveness in the workplace. The study described the level of core behavioral competencies in terms of self-management, professionalism and ethics, results focus, teamwork, service orientation and innovation; the level of teachers' job satisfaction in terms of work and workplace, supervisor and management, benefits and rewards, recognition, communication and coworker relationship; and determined the relationship between the teacher's core behavioral competencies and job satisfaction. Using the descriptive correlational method, and an adopted and modified questionnaire, 510 secondary teachers of Valencia City were surveyed. The study used the mean, standard deviation, and Pearson-r correlation in analyzing the data. Findings of the study revealed that teachers in the Division of Valencia were consistently demonstrating their core behavioral competencies. Additionally, teachers were satisfied with their jobs in terms of the variables. The correlation analysis showed a positive significant correlation between the teachers' core behavioral competencies, particularly in self-management and job satisfaction. The study proposed a teacher competency development plan to develop and improve the respondents' competencies in terms of professionalism and ethics and their job satisfaction in terms of coworker relationships. Therefore, the significant relationship observed between core behavioral competencies and teachers' job satisfaction emphasized the vital part of a high level of core competence in enhancing the teacher's job fulfillment. The study recommends investing in strategies to reinforce the development of competencies that contribute to promoting a joyful and satisfied teaching force.

Keywords: *core behavioral competencies, job satisfaction*

INTRODUCTION

Education at all levels dwells on effective teaching and learning. They are keys towards creating students who have commendable academic, socio-emotional, and behavioral well-being. Also, they are indicators of quality teachers and quality teaching performance which are relevant factors that make up a well-designed education system. Generally, teachers are considered as the most significant resources in the educational arena and their competencies impact the performance of their students. Research suggests that teachers' competencies, which are a combination of knowledge, skills, attitude and behavior, and personal characteristics, contribute to an improved quality of learning. These competencies, which include classroom management, instructional delivery, assessment, personal and behavioral, are believed to have positive impact in students' learning. Moreover, behavioral competencies of teachers are considered as one of the most important factors that influence students' performance (Soriano, 2019).

Within the Philippine context, the Department of Education (DepEd 2019) is dedicated to offering its members chances to connect their accomplishments and contribute significantly to the realization of the institution's vision and mission; to foster individual and team development, involvement and dedication professionally (DepEd, 2019). Based on this idea, DepEd uses Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS) open communication about responsibilities, goals, and key results areas—as well as how they connect to the department's overarching objectives—are made possible through the supervisor and employee's collaborative efforts. The platform that the department offers centers on the agreement upon performance and behavior standards that can lead to improvements in teachers' competencies. The teacher's effectiveness is determined by how well and consistently they demonstrate actions that are relevant to the skills, as well as by how they use their various talents to complete tasks and deliver superior performance. The DepEd's Results Based Performance Management System–Philippine Professional Standard for Teachers (RPMS-PPST) lists the following core behavioral competencies, which should be the foundation for creating a professional development plan: self-management competence, professionalism and ethics competence, results focus competence, teamwork, service orientation, and innovation (DepEdRPMS-PPST, 2021).

However, all the efforts of the government regarding training of teachers are all in vain if they choose to leave their jobs. In an article by Malipot (2022), it was reported that over 100 teachers in Cebu City resigned from service and are processing their clearances as they prepare to leave the country to work abroad. In that article, Rudy Bernardo of the Alliance of Concerned Teachers (ACT) pointed out that it is heartbreaking how teachers who started teaching full of good intentions to mentor the youth eventually got demoralized upon experiencing first-hand the system of the teaching profession in the country. Teacher job satisfaction (TJS) can be defined as the emotional reactions of teachers to their jobs or teaching roles. Ozkan (2022) cited that the job satisfaction of teachers is influenced by various elements such as school and teacher-specific attributes,

demographic shifts, and external and internal influences.

The Department of Education (DepEd) acknowledges the relevance of enhancing and equipping teachers' with skills and knowledge necessary to be able to deliver the goods to their students. However, teachers who are not satisfied with their job could not be at their best in terms of commitment and productivity. Teachers have been placed in different struggling situations which caused complains regarding too much paper works, power tripping by their superiors, students-teacher ratio, and lower salaries compared to other professionals along with loan sharks, unjustifiable monetary contributions and politics in the workplace. Hence, as a general observation, public school teachers are dissatisfied with their profession.

Further, the goal of this study was to create a Teachers Competency Development Plan (TCDP) fitted to the needs of secondary teachers of the Division of Valencia City. Such TCDP was to be anchored on their core behavioral competencies as well as their job satisfaction levels in terms of work and workplace, supervisor and management, benefits and rewards, recognition, communication and relationship with colleagues. With the help of this study, the Division Office Personnel can map ways to help develop the core behavioral competencies of the teachers as well as their level of satisfaction. Further, these contributed to the fulfillment of DepEd's long-term goal of providing inclusive and equitable quality of education and promoting lifelong learning.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the level of teachers' core behavioral competencies and job satisfaction in District 6 of the Division of Valencia City for the School Year 2024-2025. The results of the study served as bases for crafting the Teachers' Competency Development Plan.

Specifically, the study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of core behavioral competencies as perceived by the respondents in terms of self-management, professionalism and ethics, results focus, teamwork, service orientation and innovation?
2. What is the respondents' level of job satisfaction in terms of work and workplace, supervisor and management, benefits and rewards, recognition, communication and coworker relationship?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the teachers' perceived level of core behavioral competency and their job satisfaction?
4. Based on the findings of the study, what Teacher Competency Development Plan can be designed?

Research Hypothesis

Research questions 1, 2 and 4 were hypotheses – free. On the basis of research question 3, the null hypothesis was tested at a 0.05 level of significance.

Ho: There is no significant relationship between the core behavioral competencies of the teachers and their job satisfaction in terms of work and workplace, supervisor and management, benefits and rewards, recognition, communication and coworker relationship.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This research employed a descriptive correlational methods research which utilized a descriptive design to gather data and information about the core behavioral competencies of teachers as well as their job satisfaction as basis for crafting a teacher competency development plan. The study was also correlational in nature as it identified and determined the relationship between the teachers' core behavioral competencies and their job satisfaction which served as the basis for the crafting of a Teacher Competency Development Plan. Consequently, the researcher used research tools including research questionnaires alongside an interview for triangulation in order to gather data and elaborate the responses provided by the respondents. The qualitative data gathered through the interview were utilized to substantiate the quantitative responses of the respondents.

Study Setting

The research was conducted in the Division of Valencia City, Bukidnon. Valencia City is considered the most populous landlocked city in Mindanao which served as the center for trade and commerce in the province of Bukidnon. It is classified as second-class component city and has thirty- one (31) component barangays. Almost every barangay has a public primary school providing the basic education needs of its residents; the largest of which is Valencia City Central School. Secondary education has also been made accessible to all students by legislating integrated schools almost in every barangay. Educational institutions within the city are a combination of public and private schools. Presently, Division of Valencia City serves the community with thirty-four (34) Elementary Schools, twenty-six (26) Integrated School and seven (7) National High Schools.

Research Respondents

The respondents of the study were the five hundred ten (510) secondary school teachers of the Division of Valencia City for the school year 2023-2024.

Sampling Technique

The research utilized purposive sampling in identifying the Integrated Schools to be considered as respondents of the study since there were integrated schools with only a few teachers. On the other hand, the respondents from Valencia National High School, a mega school, were identified using the Slovin's formula.

Research Instruments

In the first part, the research used DepEd's Results-Based Performance Management System–Philippine Professional Standard for Teachers (RPMS-PPST) list of behavioral competencies, which includes self-management competence, professionalism and ethics competence, results focus competence, teamwork, service orientation, and innovation (DepEd RPMS-PPST, 2021) in order to identify and determine the level of teachers' competencies. It is a standardized tool that uses a Likert Scale starting with 1 being the scale, which means that the teacher respondent is hardly demonstrating the said competency up to five which signifies that the teacher is considered a role model in terms of demonstrating the competencies.

Part 2 is a tool patterned from the study of Troeger (2021) used to determine the teachers' perceived level of job satisfaction in terms of work and workplace, supervision and management, benefits and rewards, recognition, communication and relationships with co-teachers. It uses a 5-point Likert Scale with one (1) signifying a high level of dissatisfaction and five embodying a high level of satisfaction. An Interview was carried out to support, enhance and substantiate the responses of the teachers. Part 3 consists of six (6) questions, which triangulated the data in the other parts. It served as the part that yielded the qualitative responses from the respondents that substantiated the results.

The third part of the questionnaire consists of 6 open-ended questions to substantiate the numerical responses of the respondents.

Validity and Reliability

In this study, Part 1 of the questionnaire is a standardized instrument based on the DepEd Order 2, s. 2015, the National Adoption and Implementation of the Philippine Professional Standards provides the standard for the questionnaire. Therefore, there was no need for a test of validity and reliability. However, in Part 2, the teacher-made questionnaire underwent a validity test and pilot testing to determine its reliability. The questionnaire was validated by experts with a score of 4.86, which signified that the questionnaire demonstrates very high validity, ensuring the provision of unbiased data for the investigation.

To test its reliability, the questionnaire was pilot-tested to schools not part of those considered as respondents but having the same characteristics as them. The instrument was tested last June 4, 2024, at Banlag Integrated School and Lumbo Integrated School. It was good to note the teachers who answered the instrument for pilot-testing understood the statements and did not have any queries as to the meaning of the statements

provided. The reliability analysis of the instrument yielded the Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.980 which indicated that the items have high level of consistency.

Additionally, the respondents answered open-ended questions to substantiate the numerical responses. After gathering all the responses, the results were subjected to a reliability test where the Cronbach's Alpha was measured and interpreted using SPSS.

Data Gathering Procedure

Upon the approval of the proposal by the Dean of Graduate Studies of PHINMA Cagayan de Oro College, the researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of Valencia City where the study will be conducted with the approved letter. In the gathering of data, the researcher administered the questionnaires in the pre-identified schools in the above-mentioned division. The researcher followed the protocol of asking permission from each school's principal and school head before requesting the teachers to answer the questionnaires. The researcher made sure that she was available should there be queries from the respondents about how they answered the questions. After the questionnaires were collected, responses were tallied and recorded accurately. The data gathered underwent the necessary and corresponding statistical procedures. Additionally, researcher conducted a methodological triangulation to validate the responses and substantiate the results. Qualitative answers of the responses were recorded and used to substantiate the numerical responses. All information obtained from the questionnaire and interviews were considered confidential.

System of Scoring

This study utilized the following scoring system that allowed an objective assessment of the answers of the respondents. Additionally, the scoring procedure provided a quantitative measure for evaluating the level of core behavioral competencies and the job satisfaction of the respondents.

PART I. Core Behavioral Competencies

Scale	Range	Description	Interpretation
5	4.50 – 5.00	Always	Role Model
4	3.50 – 4.49	Very Often	Consistently Demonstrates
3	2.50 – 3.49	Sometimes	Occasionally Demonstrates
2	1.50- 2.49	Rarely	Inconsistently Demonstrates
1	below 1.49	Never	Hardly Demonstrates

PART II. Teachers' Job Satisfaction

Scale	Range	Description	Interpretation
5	4.50 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very Satisfied
4	3.50 – 4.49	Agree	Satisfied
3	2.50 – 3.49	Neutral	Undecided
2	1.50 - 2.49	Disagree	Dissatisfied
1	below 1.49	Strongly Disagree	Very Dissatisfied

Statistical Treatment of Data

To answer the problems stated in this study, the researcher employed statistical procedures. Descriptive Statistics was used in finding the level of core behavioral competencies of the respondents in terms of the variables. Here, the mean, as the preferred measure of central tendency, was used to describe the responses based on the scale. Standard Deviation was also identified in order to describe how dispersed were the responses of the participants. Additionally, to find the relationship between the core behavioral competencies and teachers' job satisfaction, the research employed the Pearson r Coefficient.

Scope and Limitation

This study limited its scope in assessing the perceived level of core behavioral competencies in terms of the following specific sub-variables such as self-management, professionalism and ethics, results-focus, teamwork, service orientation and innovation. Other factors and variables not included thereof are beyond the scope of this study. This study is also constrained only to secondary teachers within the Division of Valencia City for the School Year 2024-2025.

Furthermore, the study delimited itself to the perceived level of teachers' job satisfaction in terms of work and workplace, supervisor and management, benefits and rewards, recognition, communication and coworker relationship. Moreover, this research endeavor aimed to propose a Teacher Competency Development Plan (TCDP) which will help in equipping teachers of the necessary core behavioral competencies.

The research involved the five hundred six (506) respondents of in-service basic education teachers of the Division of Valencia City. These respondents came from pre-selected Integrated Schools and all the National High Schools within the Division. To ensure a comprehensive and reliable representation, it exclusively involved teachers from public schools.

RESULTS

Research Question 1. What is the level of core behavioral competencies as perceived by the respondents in terms of self-management, professionalism and ethics, results focus, teamwork, service orientation and innovation?

This research recognized the various competencies of educators in the field to provide quality education among learners. It focuses on determining the level of core behavioral competencies of the respondents in terms of self-management, professionalism and ethics, results focus, teamwork, service orientation and innovation.

By understanding the level of the respondents' core behavioral competencies, researchers can identify patterns and trends with respect to the competencies possessed by the respondents as well as those competencies they need to improve on. This information can inform directed interventions and support mechanisms to address the developmental needs of teachers.

Table 1 Distribution of Respondents' Level of Core Behavioral Competencies in terms of Self-Management

Indicators	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
Sets personal goals and directions, needs and development.	3.44	0.66	Sometimes
Undertakes personal actions and behaviour that are clear and purposive and takes into account personal goals and values congruent to that of the organization.	3.78	0.58	Very Often
Displays emotional maturity and enthusiasm for and is challenged by higher goals.	3.87	0.69	Very Often
Prioritizes work tasks and schedules (through Gantt charts, checklists, etc.) to achieve goals.	3.70	0.63	Very Often
Sets high quality, challenging, realistic goals for self and others.	3.74	0.51	Very Often
Overall	3.69	0.39	Very Often

Legend:

4.50 – 5.00	Always/Role Model	1.50- 2.49	Rarely/Inconsistently Demonstrates
3.50 – 4.49	Very Often/Consistently Demonstrates	1.49 below	Never/Hardly Demonstrates
2.50 – 3.49	Sometimes/Occasionally Demonstrates		

Table 1 presents the respondents' core behavioral competencies in terms of self-management with an overall mean of 3.69 (SD=0.39), described as Very Often and interpreted as Consistently Demonstrates. These results highlight the ability of the respondents to manage their own emotions, behaviors, work, and time. Teachers'

emotional intelligence is crucial for creating a positive learning environment as well as support students' emotional development. When teachers are able to regulate their emotions and behavior, they can better respond to challenging situations, build strong relationships and model healthy emotional expression. Results validated the study of Smith (2022) when he opined that teachers with high self-management are better able to manage their own emotions, effectively implement strategies to address difficulties both personally and professionally and practice self-care.

However, teaching can be emotionally and mentally demanding, and teachers often experience a range of extreme emotions. Unmanaged negative emotions like anger or stress can disrupt teacher-students relationship, impair teaching effectiveness and lead to burn out.

Additionally, the highest-rated indicator, display emotional maturity and enthusiasm for and is challenged by higher goals, got a mean of 3.87 (SD=0.69), described as Sometimes and interpreted as Occasionally Demonstrates. These marks focus on the importance of modeling emotional regulation and coping skills, creating a healthy and conducive workplace and being open to continuous learning. Emotionally mature teachers are better able to respond constructively to challenging situations and build strong and supportive relationships with students. Moreover, enthusiastic teachers demonstrate excitement and energy about the subject matter use varied strategies to capture students' interests and inspire students to be more curious and motivated to learn. This is supported by the study of Bieg (2022), which emphasized that enthusiasm has a direct impact on students' emotions and engagement in educational settings.

Conversely, the indicator set personal goals and directions, needs and development got the lowest mean of 3.44 (SD=0.66), described as Sometimes and interpreted as Occasionally Demonstrates. This means that teachers' are making sure their goals are reached as advocated by their leaders.

As a result, they tend to set relatively low goals and avoid those that are challenging and difficult. Teachers may be hesitant to set overly ambitious or difficult goals because of fear of failure. To them, challenging goals carry a higher risk of not being met, which can be demotivating for both teachers and students. Also, teachers already have a heavy workload, and adding very difficult goals can feel like an unmanageable burden. They may prioritize maintaining a sustainable pace over striving for stretch goals.

Another culprit to teachers setting low goals in the lack of resources that could sustain the accomplishment of the goals. Achieving ambitious goals often requires additional time, training, or materials that teachers may not have access to. The perceived lack of support can discourage setting such goals. Likewise, in terms of teaching and learning, teachers avoid setting the bars too high for students because this could undermine their confidence if they struggle to meet such goals. Hence, teachers may opt for more modest and achievable targets.

This finding negates the study of Odindo (2020), which said that Filipino teachers' strategies were above average indicating a strong ability to set high goals. Accordingly,

Filipino teachers are highly motivated to set high goals by intrinsic factors like commitment to the profession, belief in the divine providence and a desire to bring about positive change and transform the lives of their students. Emphasis on goal setting among Filipino teachers reflects a broader commitment to personal growth, effective teaching practices and the empowerment of students.

Table 2 Distribution of Respondents' Level of Core Behavioral Competencies in terms of Professionalism and Ethics

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
Demonstrates the values and behaviour enshrined in the Norms and Conduct and Ethical Standards for public officials and employees (RA 6713).	3.75	0.53	Very Often
Practices ethical and professional behaviour and conduct taking into account the impact of his/her actions and decisions.	3.70	0.58	Very Often
Maintains a professional image: being trustworthy, regularity of attendance and punctuality, good grooming and communication.	3.61	0.57	Very Often
Makes personal sacrifices to meet the organization's needs.	3.64	0.60	Very Often
Act with a sense of urgency and responsibility to meet the organization's needs, improve system and help others improve their effectiveness.	3.67	0.51	Very Often
Overall	3.67	0.42	Very Often

Legend:

4.50 – 5.00	Always/Role Model	1.50- 2.49	Rarely/Inconsistently Demonstrates
3.50 – 4.49	Very Often/Consistently Demonstrates	1.49 below	Never/Hardly Demonstrates
2.50 – 3.49	Sometimes/Occasionally Demonstrates		

Table 2 shows the distribution of respondents' level of core behavioral competencies terms professionalism and ethics with an overall mean score of 3.67 (SD=0.42), described as Very Often and interpreted as Consistently Demonstrates. This means that teachers actively manifest the attributes mentioned above, as evidenced by the consistently high mean scores and low standard deviations.

These results display the obligation of the teachers to the teaching profession. They exhibit a strong commitment driven by intrinsic motivations like their belief in their role as trustees of the nation's cultural and educational heritage and their desire to elevate national morality, promote pride and instill allegiance to the constitution. Also, they are focused and dedicated to prepare students for life and transforming lives through education. This relates to the study of Dahl (2020) which emphasized that professionalism is demonstrated by practitioners taking charge of their work because they are the best ones who comprehend its objectives, procedures, and results.

The indicator, demonstrate the values and behavior enshrined in the Norms and Conduct and Ethical Standards for public officials and employees (RA 6713), obtained

the highest mean score of 3.75 (SD=0.53), described as Very Often and interpreted as Consistently Demonstrates. This means that teachers within the locale are well informed of the expected attitude and behavior from the teachers based on professional and ethical standards. The key elements included in these standards emphasize that public officials should maintain physical, mental and moral fitness, demonstrate full commitment and devotion to duty, refrain from engaging in political, religious or partisan interests, behave with honor and dignity and continually improve one's competence through professional development.

Fernandes (2023) pointed out that maintaining a professional demeanor and upholding the highest standards of conduct is crucial for teachers to serve as effective role models for their students and the community. However, Gumahad (2023), in his study on teachers' compliance with RA6713, perceived that some teachers may prioritize benefits and privileges over their duties which negatively impact their professionalism and adherence to ethical standards.

On the other hand, maintain a professional image: being trustworthy, regularity of attendance and punctuality, good grooming and communication obtained the lowest, with a mean score of 3.61 (SD=0.57), described as Very Often and interpreted as Consistently Demonstrates. Being punctual demonstrates respect for clients, colleagues, superiors and the whole school community. In the locale, the office of the ASDS served an instruction to closely monitor the attendance and punctuality of the teachers. This is done by authorizing the school heads to report the frequency of teachers' tardiness and absences. This action was caused by the alarming number of teachers who were found to have incurred frequent tardiness and absences. In a study by Johnsons (2023), she opined that punctuality sets the tone for a productive and organized working environment. Additionally, it is the key aspect of professionalism that helps teachers in modeling responsible behavior for their students.

Additionally, professionalism, as described by Kramer (2023), is when a teacher must focus on the critical elements of attitude, behavior and communication. Assumptions that K to 12 teacher candidates will simply become professionals as a result of completing the teacher education program and that professional dispositions will be automatically acquired through field experiences are common in the field of teacher education. One of the things that have historically distinguished professionals is their different professional expertise (Choroszewicz & Adams, 2019). It comes after that preliminary instruction and ongoing professional development.

Table 3 Distribution of Respondents' Level of Core Behavioral Competencies in terms of Results Focus

Indicators	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
Achieves results with optimal use of time and resources most of the time.	4.15	0.52	Very Often

Avoids rework, mistakes and wastage through effective work methods by placing organizational needs before personal needs.	3.82	0.67	Very Often
Delivers error-free outputs most of the time by conforming to standard operating procedures correctly and consistently. Able to produce very satisfactory quality work in terms of usefulness/acceptability and completeness with no supervision required.	3.95	0.63	Very Often
Expresses a desire to do better and may express frustration at waste or inefficiency. May focus on new or more precise ways of meeting goals set.	3.92	0.72	Very Often
Makes specific changes in the system or in own work methods to improve performance. Examples may include doing something better, faster, at a lower cost, more efficiently, or improving quality, customer satisfaction, morale, without setting any specific goal.	3.99	0.43	Very Often
Overall	3.97	0.41	Very Often

Legend:

4.50 – 5.00	Always/Role Model	1.50- 2.49	Rarely/Inconsistently Demonstrates
3.50 – 4.49	Very Often/Consistently Demonstrates	1.49 below	Never/Hardly Demonstrates
2.50 – 3.49	Sometimes/Occasionally Demonstrates		

Table 3 shows the teacher respondents' level of behavioral display competence in terms of results focus with an overall mean 3.97 (SD=0.41) described as Very Often and interpreted as Consistently Demonstrates. A teacher who possesses this competency makes sure that every student reaches his/her full potential through methodical lesson delivery, constant monitoring and evaluation of students' achievements. In the context of the respondents' locale, timeliness in terms of submission of reports, and the like is being recognized. It has already been a practice that those schools with is being recognized. It has already been a practice that those schools with prompt submissions are given awards and recognition. These reports are coming from dedicated teachers. Hence, respondents are considered competent in terms of being results-focused. In a study by Alyami et al. (2021), they mentioned Filipino Teachers' timeliness to impact student performance. Effective time management by teachers is crucial for ensuring that students receive adequate instruction and support, which in turn enhances their academic achievement.

The indicator achieves results with optimal use of time and resources most of the time got the highest mean of 4.15 (SD=0.52), described as Very Often and interpreted as Consistently Demonstrates. It means that the teachers consistently demonstrate core behavioral competencies in terms of results focus. It suggests that teacher respondents in the locale indeed maximize their time and resources in achieving their goals. For instance, strict implementation of classroom program as well as teachers' individual schedule is closely monitored by district supervisors to ensure contact time with students is maximized. However, as observed, teachers are often overworked-spending additional hours outside paid working hours. This excessive workload takes a toll on their personal lives, well-being and ability to provide quality education.

Additionally, many teachers lack the necessary resources and support to be effective in the classroom. These struggles caused teachers to be exacerbated by their heavy workloads and limited resources. Despite the struggles, teachers are trying their best to find ways to optimize their time and resources by leveraging technology for efficiency. They believe that technology helps them to save time, personalize instructions and foster students' engagement more effectively. Results conform to the article by Cuballa (2023), which says that although teachers are faced with struggles on limited resources and facilities, majority of them are still fueled by their passion to educate young minds.

Conversely, the indicator avoids rework, mistakes and wastage through effective work methods by placing organizational needs before personal needs got the lowest with a mean of 3.82 (SD=0.67), described as Very Often and interpreted as Consistently Demonstrates. Although it is the lowest among the indicators, still it means that the respondents consistently demonstrate the results focus. Results suggest that teachers demonstrate a high ability to compartmentalize their personal problems and emotions. They are able to set aside their own issues and display professional dispositions when interacting with students in the classroom. This compartmentalization skill allows them to prioritize their teaching responsibilities and organizational needs over their personal needs. However, since teachers in the locale are closely monitored in terms of time on tasks, whenever they are required to submit documents, they tend to do it the fastest way they can somehow compromising the correctness of the said document. This confirms the finding of Earp (2022), which was stated in an article that highlights that an overwhelming majority of teachers don't get enough time to prepare for effective teaching practices or high-quality planning of lessons.

Table 4 Distribution of Respondents' Level of Core Behavioral Competencies in terms of Teamwork

Indicators	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
Willingly does his/her share of responsibility.	4.00	0.44	Very Often
Promotes collaboration and removes barrier to teamwork and goal accomplishment across the organization.	3.80	0.70	Very Often
Applies negotiation principles in arriving at win-win agreements.	4.21	0.62	Very Often
Drives consensus and team ownership of decisions.	4.01	0.74	Very Often
Works constructively and collaboratively with others and across organizations to accomplish organization goals and objectives.	3.81	0.40	Very Often
Overall	3.97	0.39	Very Often

Legend:

4.50 – 5.00	Always/Role Model	1.50- 2.49	Rarely/Inconsistently Demonstrates
3.50 – 4.49	Very Often/Consistently Demonstrates	1.49 below	Never/Hardly Demonstrates
2.50 – 3.49	Sometimes/Occasionally Demonstrates		

Table 4 overall shows the respondents' core behavioral competencies in terms of teamwork with an overall mean of 3.97 (SD=0.39), described as Very Often and interpreted as Consistently Demonstrates. This means that teachers in the locale collaborate with each other allowing them to pool their knowledge and find innovative solutions to common challenges. Moreover, the role of teacher collaboration in improving instructional effectiveness is crucial because when teachers work together, they are able to share resources and teaching strategies, engage in collective problem-solving and foster a culture of continuous improvement and shared responsibility.

The results of this study is supported by the study of Polega,et.al (2019) which concluded that almost all of the principals rated teamwork as highly important in the workplace, with only 1.1% attributing low importance to it. Additionally, in the same study, it was highlighted that principals considered teamwork important for school culture and success, student achievement, and teachers' pedagogical practices and personal growth.

The indicator, applies negotiation principles in arriving at win-win agreements obtained the highest a mean score of 4.21 (SD=0.62), described as Very Often and interpreted as Consistently Demonstrates. It means that the respondents consistently demonstrate core behavioral competencies in terms of teamwork. This suggests that majority of the respondents do their best to maintain harmony and peace in the workplace. Moreover, in the locale, this ability to arrive at win-win agreements is further strengthened by the revitalization of the School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) sessions. Although it is focused on students' improvement, it has become an avenue for teachers to bond, reconcile and resolve issues within their small groups, preventing more conflicts within the entire school. Results conformed to the study of Binauhan (2019), which enumerated the benefits of SLAC in enhancing the performance of the teachers. According to her, the benefits include improvement of teachers' practices, enhancement of professional development, increased teacher support and improved teachers' relationship with colleagues.

However, the indicator, promoting collaboration and removing barrier to teamwork and goal accomplishment across the organization, got the lowest mean of 3.80 (SD=0.70), described as Very Often and interpreted as Consistently Demonstrates. This suggests that teachers in the locale are having difficulties in barriers means that teachers have to promote trust and open communication amongst them, align everyone towards a common and shared vision for collaboration and provide structured opportunities for their colleagues to work together. When teachers feel psychologically safe and have a clear sense of purpose, they are more likely to engage in productive teamwork.

The results of this study confirmed the study of Bishnoi (2023) which concluded that teachers are the foundation of our schools' success; they are the greatest resource for each other. Strong schools are built through effective teacher collaboration. The same study emphasized that time constraints and relationship concerns are common barriers to teamwork among teachers. It is essential for schools to allocate sufficient time for teachers to collaborate and share ideas.

Additionally, Bishnoi (2023) suggested in his study that directly training teachers on essential teamwork competencies can help them overcome common barriers. This includes effective communication and active listening, conflict resolution, goal-setting and task coordination, and providing and receiving constructive feedback.

Table 5 Distribution of Respondents' Level of Core Behavioral Competencies in terms of Service Orientation

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
Can explain and articulate organizational directions, issues and problems.	3.99	0.44	Very Often
Takes personal responsibility for dealing with and/or correcting customer service issues and concerns.	3.97	0.69	Very Often
Initiates activities that promote advocacy for men and women empowerment.	3.79	0.61	Very Often
in updating office vision, mission, mandates and strategies based on DEPED strategies and directions.	3.81	0.73	Very Often
Develops and adopts service improvement program through simplified procedures that will further enhance service delivery.	4.25	0.39	Very Often
Overall	3.96	0.38	Very Often

Legend:

4.50 – 5.00	Always/Role Model	1.50- 2.49	Rarely/Inconsistently Demonstrates
3.50 – 4.49	Very Often/Consistently Demonstrates	1.49 below	Never/Hardly Demonstrates
2.50 – 3.49	Sometimes/Occasionally Demonstrates		

Table 5 shows the respondents' core behavioral competencies in terms of service orientation with an overall mean score of 3.96 (SD=0.38), described as Very Often and interpreted as Consistently Demonstrates. This means that teachers exhibit quality in the majority of the assessed areas, as evidenced by the consistently high mean scores and low standard deviations. In the locale of the study, Teachers' Induction Program (TIP) has been conducted prior to the deployment of newly-hired teachers. In this program, they are totally informed of everything that they need to know especially when they are already in the field. More importantly, they aim to prepare teachers and make sure that their commitment is all out before they will be immersed in the real world of teaching and learning. The results of this study confirmed the findings of Agustin (2022) which demonstrates that Filipino teachers exhibit strong pedagogical competence, subject matter knowledge, and dedication to professional development which are also key indicators of service orientation.

The indicator develop and adopt service improvement program through simplified procedures that will further enhance service delivery obtained the highest mean score of 4.25 (SD=0.39), described as Very Often, and interpreted as Consistently Demonstrates. This means that most of the teachers in the locale are into developing schemes that will make service delivery more efficient and effective. In this aspect, the role of educational

technology in helping teachers streamline administrative tasks and focus more on the students is being highlighted. Contextually, the use of electronic class records is one of the examples of schemes that make tasks easier and faster to accomplish. This innovation of the department has made positive impacts in the educational arena and has given the teachers additional time for teacher-student interaction. According to Keshavdas (2023), the ability focus on the essentials and simplify processes will unlock significant benefits across the organization.

On the other hand, the indicator initiate activities that promote advocacy for men and women empowerment, obtained the lowest mean score of 3.79 (SD=0.61), described as Very Often and interpreted as Consistently Demonstrates. Indeed respondents in the locale have limited opportunities in terms of initiating programs to promote men and women empowerment. This may be attributed to the fact that when it comes to empowering teachers, they are taken as one and not based on gender. However, respondents acknowledge that through this, a more inclusive and sustainable approach to gender equality, ultimately leading to greater economic empowerment development for women will be created. This is supported by the study Perines (2020) which focused on designing a teacher training program to raise awareness about gender and social issues in academic settings and society.

Table 6 Distribution of Respondents' Level of Core Behavioral Competencies in terms of Innovation

Indicators	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
Examines the root cause of problems and suggests effective solutions. Foster new ideas, processes and suggests better ways to do things (cost and/ or operational efficiency).	3.98	0.39	Very Often
Demonstrates an ability to think "beyond the box". Continuously focuses on improving personal productivity to create higher value and results.	3.58	0.67	Very Often
Promotes a creative climate and inspires co-workers to develop original ideas or solutions.	4.42	0.53	Very Often
Translates creative thinking into tangible changes and solutions that improve the work unit and organization.	3.90	0.57	Very Often
Uses ingenious methods to accomplish responsibilities. Demonstrates resourcefulness and the ability to succeed with minimal resources.	3.81	0.39	Very Often
Overall	3.94	0.26	Very Often

Legend:

4.50 – 5.00	Always/Role Model	1.50- 2.49	Rarely/Inconsistently Demonstrates
3.50 – 4.49	Very Often/Consistently Demonstrates	1.49 below	Never/Hardly Demonstrates
2.50 – 3.49	Sometimes/Occasionally Demonstrates		

Table 6 presents the respondents' core behavioral competencies in terms of innovation with an overall mean score of 3.94 (SD=0.26), described as Very Often and interpreted as Consistently Demonstrates. This means that respondents extensively demonstrate innovative skills in their teaching job. The locale of the study is a strong advocate for new pedagogies and teaching strategies that are products of action researches and innovations. In fact, SDO-CID annually initiates a research and innovations

Congress where teachers are able to share the results of their research endeavors. These activities motivate teachers to conduct more researches so as to address the problems at hand. This is supported by the study of Ortile (2023) where he opined that Filipino teachers have implemented various innovative teaching strategies such as using online game, memes, and social media to engage students and enhance learning outcomes.

Among the indicators, promote a creative climate and inspire co-workers to develop original ideas or solutions, obtained the highest mean of 4.42 (SD=0.53), described as Very Often and interpreted as Consistently Demonstrates. This means that a great number of the teacher respondents are into inspiring their colleagues to authentic and be divergent thinkers. When teachers receive structured opportunities to work together, they are more likely to experiment with new teaching methods, engage in continuous improvement and inspire each other to push the boundaries of their practice. The results of this study are supported by the paper of Froehlich (2021) who emphasized that divergent thinking helps teachers overcome the tendency to work within the confines of fixed mindsets. Hence, it fosters the creativity and problem-solving skills of the teachers.

On the other hand, the indicator, demonstrating an ability to think “beyond the box” and continuously focusing on improving personal productivity to create higher value and results, obtained the lowest mean of 3.58 (SD=.673), described as Very Often and interpreted as Consistently Demonstrates. This suggests that teachers who think outside the box are able to challenge the status quo and traditional paradigms in education. They are not afraid to try alternative approaches that may integrate language with skills, content with language, and old with new methodologies. These teachers recognize that progress often comes from invading other fields and disciplines beyond just education. Thinking outside the box requires teachers to develop confidence in their own decision-making abilities and expertise. It involves taking risks, being creative, and not being limited by the constraints of the institution or profession. Teachers who are bored with the current state of education or need to adjust to imposed changes are often motivated to think outside the box

Conversely, there are respondents who also think traditionally which is alarming because educators are expected to be strong advocates for continuous learning. Results confirmed the study of Bautista (2023) when she said that Filipino teachers have been slow in shifting from traditional to divergent thinking. They struggle to adopt progressive teaching methods, such as student-centered approaches, personalized learning and diverse assessments which are more effective in developing critical thinking.

Table 7 Summary of the Respondents’ Level of Core Behavioral Competencies

Variables	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Self-Management	3.69	0.40	Consistently Demonstrates
Professionalism and Ethics	3.67	0.42	Consistently Demonstrates
Results-focus	3.97	0.41	Consistently Demonstrates
	3.97	0.39	

Teamwork			Consistently Demonstrates
Service Orientation	3.96	0.38	Consistently Demonstrates
Innovation	3.94	0.26	Consistently Demonstrates
Overall	3.78	0.38	Consistently Demonstrates

Legend:

4.50 – 5.00	Always/Role Model	1.50- 2.49	Rarely/Inconsistently Demonstrates
3.50 – 4.49	Very Often/Consistently Demonstrates	1.49 below	Never/Hardly Demonstrates
2.50 – 3.49	Sometimes/Occasionally Demonstrates		

Table 7 reflects the summary of the respondents' level of core behavioral competencies with an overall mean of 3.78 (SD=0.38), interpreted as Consistently Demonstrates. This means that the teachers with high levels of core behavioral competencies, particularly tend to exhibit stronger teaching performance and more positive work attitudes. Cultivating these behavioral competencies appears to be a key lever for improving overall teacher effectiveness.

As detailed in the table, results focus had the highest mean score of 3.97 (SD=0.41), interpreted as Consistently Demonstrates. Being results-focused is a skill necessary for teachers to thrive in the workplace. Results-focused teachers understand that by prioritizing student mastery, engagement and growth, the desired academic outcomes will follow. They are driven by a commitment to helping each student reach their full potential, maintain a positive, enthusiastic classroom environment that motivates students to take ownership of their learning and reflect regularly on the effectiveness of their teaching seeking out opportunities for professional growth and development.

Moreover, teachers with a strong results focus are able to consistently set and achieve ambitious goals for their students. They are proactive, persistent, and motivated in pursuing their objectives to maximize student learning and performance. These teachers direct their efforts toward accomplishing desired outcomes and are not deterred by obstacles or challenges. This finding is in accordance with the findings reported by Rabotan (2019) who said that a teacher that is results-focused is dedicated to making sure that each student learns as much as they can and realizes their maximum potential. They use a methodical approach to lesson design and delivery, emphasizing the clear explanation of learning objectives, giving students practical chances and feedback, and routinely assessing their techniques to raise student accomplishment.

Furthermore, teamwork also is the highest-rated variable with a mean score of 3.97 (SD=0.39), interpreted as Consistently Demonstrates. Highly competent teachers who work in a team are able to foster a sense of shared responsibility and accountability among their colleagues. They encourage open communication, mutual trust, and a commitment to the team's collective success. Effective teamwork allows teachers to leverage each other's strengths, improve problem-solving, and enhance overall productivity. Teachers who demonstrate strong teamwork abilities can collaborate effectively with colleagues, communicate openly, and contribute positively to the school community. They establish professional learning communities to work together towards shared goals.

Teamwork is an essential strategy for teachers to tackle complex challenges. By sharing their knowledge and perspectives, teachers can better identify early warning signs of student-related problems and intervene more effectively. In the interview conducted by the researcher, the respondents emphasized that relationship with colleagues is crucial to the well-being of teachers and it has a huge impact on how teachers manage their jobs. This result is in conformity with the study of Cruszos (2022) which stated that teachers consistently showed satisfactory level of competencies in areas such as self-management, teamwork and service orientation.

Furthermore, it can also be seen in the table that professionalism and ethics had the lowest mean score of 3.67 (SD=0.42), interpreted as Consistently Demonstrate. In the locale, although there are already a lot of seasoned teachers already, still there is a need for them to be reminded as to the level of professionalism and ethics that they need to display. Consequently, in response, the division office has been doing its best to educate and encourage the teaching personnel to be informed and as much as possible, find the initiative to review the standard by revisiting the legal bases such as the DepEd orders.

Professionalism and strong ethical standards are considered essential for teachers to be effective in their roles. They serve as the foundation for all other teaching competencies. When teachers demonstrate integrity, respect, and service to others, they reinforce these values in their students. When teachers model these qualities, it promotes equality, non-discrimination, and a spirit of teamwork among all staff. Thus, it is crucial to maintain a high ethical standards helps preserve the reputation and integrity of the teaching profession and the school as a whole.

In a study by Keshmiri et al. (2023), it was clearly stated that professionalism and ethics are important in the teaching profession because teachers are expected to adhere to professional ethics which include commitment to students' success, maintaining ethical standards, and being role models for their students and colleagues. Moreover, according to the same author, teachers should engage in continuous professional development to improve their skills and maintain their professional standards.

Research Question 2. What is the respondents' level of job satisfaction in terms of work and workplace, supervisor and management, benefits and rewards, recognition, communication and coworker relationship?

Teachers are essential to the success of the education system, so it is vital that they are satisfied with their working conditions in order to perform well and deliver quality education to students. Job satisfaction is closely related to teacher retention, as well as the overall well-being of teachers and their students, school cohesion, and the status of the teaching profession.

Table 8 Distribution of Teachers' Level of Job Satisfaction in terms of Work and Workplace

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
Doing my work is pleasurable.	4.24	0.72	Agree
Working conditions in my school are comfortable.	4.25	0.68	Agree
Teaching provides me the chance to develop new methods by being part of trainings, webinars, meetings and outreach activities.	4.24	0.74	Agree
The information, tools and resources I need to do my job effectively, have been provided for me.	4.19	0.73	Agree
What is expected of me at work was discussed to me prior to every given task.	4.32	0.72	Agree
Making decisions to solve problems for my clients is encouraged in my workplace	4.22	0.70	Agree
I know how to measure the quality of my work	4.27	0.70	Agree
My workplace is safe and secured.	4.31	0.74	Agree
I would not consider leaving my job for another with greater opportunities for advancement.	4.21	0.77	Agree
My job has high value to the community.	4.40	0.68	Agree
Overall	4.26	0.72	Agree

Legend:

4.50 – 5.00	Strongly Agree/Very Satisfied	1.50 - 2.49	Disagree/Dissatisfied
3.50 – 4.49	Agree/Satisfied	1.49 below	Strongly Disagree/ Very Dissatisfied
2.50 – 3.49	Neutral/Undecided		

Table 8 shows the distribution of teachers' level of job satisfaction in terms of work and workplace with an overall mean score of 4.26 (SD=0.72) described as Agree and interpreted as Satisfied. When teachers are satisfied in their work and workplace, they are more emotionally adaptive, motivated and successful in their roles. Satisfied teachers are better able to thrive and deliver quality instruction that helps students succeed academically. Also, teachers who are happy in their work and workplace are most likely to go to work every day feeling motivated eventually being productive for the day.

These results confirmed with the study of Hoque (2023), in which workplace was highlighted as more strongly associated with teacher satisfaction compared to background factors, gender, years of experience, and school characteristics. Gomez (2023) also emphasized the substantial impact of workplace conditions on teacher satisfaction, highlighting factors such as administrative support, leadership, student behavior, school atmosphere, and teacher autonomy as crucial determinants of job contentment.

The indicator, the job has a high value to the community, obtained a highest mean score of 4.40 (SD=0.68), described as Agree and interpreted as Satisfied. In the interview part of this study, a good number of teachers narrated that they are happy with the amount of respect they receive from the community. However, there were also other who said that the amount of respect that teachers receive nowadays is way lesser than that years ago. This agrees with the study Fabella (2022), where she opined that Filipino teachers

face significant challenges in terms of social status, professional image and community respect.

Furthermore, the results of this study abide by Spence (2022) when he said that the value of the teaching job in the community is crucial for their role in the society. This value is demonstrated in the teachers' community development, role modeling, holistic and professional development. Results also relates to the study conducted by SEAMEO Innotech (2021) which found that teachers decided to stay to help students and contribute to society. Their passion lies in teaching, and they are proud that teachers are highly respected in their communities.

However, the indicator The information, tools and resources that teachers need to do their jobs effectively, have been provided for them, got the lowest mean score of 4.19 (SD=0.73), described as Agree and interpreted as Satisfied. This suggests that they are still contented despite the disparity of this indicator's mean compared to the rest of the indicators. When teachers are provided with the right mix of curriculum resources, classroom tools, professional development, and financial support, they are empowered to do their jobs more effectively and efficiently. This ultimately leads to higher teacher satisfaction, retention and student outcomes. However, in the study of Baluyos et al. (2019), it was found out that those Filipino teachers face significant challenges in terms of resources, infrastructures and support systems which can impact their ability to effectively teach and contribute to the education system.

Alibang (2023), opined that Filipino teachers, who play an important role in shaping the brains of the country's future, are frequently at the forefront of these daunting challenges. From low salaries to a shortage of resources, these dedicated instructors face a complex web of obstacles that affect not just their teaching methods but also the quality of education for countless children.

Table 9 Distribution of Teachers' Level of Job Satisfaction in terms of Supervisor and Management

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
The organization where I am in has the right people and skills to do its work.	4.25	0.67	Agree
The organization practices high standards and ethics.	4.26	0.65	Agree
My superior is competent in doing his/her job.	4.31	0.66	Agree
My superior shows interest in my feelings and acknowledge my concerns.	4.21	0.68	Agree
My superior acknowledges my achievements and contribution in the organization.	4.59	0.65	Strongly Agree
My superior shows empathy whenever I have struggles both personally and professionally.	4.29	0.65	Agree

My superior holds me and colleagues accountable for our performance.	4.30	0.64	Agree
My superior is reliable.	4.32	0.70	Agree
The administration in my school communicates its policies well.	4.28	0.72	Agree
There is access to the management whenever the superior does not listen.	3.38	0.67	Neutral
Overall	4.22	0.67	Agree

Legend:

4.50 – 5.00	Strongly Agree/Very Satisfied	1.50 - 2.49	Disagree/Dissatisfied
3.50 – 4.49	Agree/Satisfied	1.49 below	Strongly Disagree/ Very Dissatisfied
2.50 – 3.49	Neutral/Undecided		

Table 9 shows the distribution of teachers' level of job satisfaction in terms of supervisor and management with an overall mean of 4.22 (SD=0.67) described as Agree and interpreted as Satisfied. Teachers who feel supported, empowered and respected by their administrators tend to be more satisfied and engaged in their work. When teachers feel their administrators are competent, fair and supportive, it enhances their job satisfaction, motivation and commitment to the school's mission. This in turn leads to higher teacher retention, instructional quality, and ultimately improved student outcomes. This result is supported by the study of Gomez (2023) which said that Filipino teachers in the public schools agree that they are satisfied with the organization's leadership. Moreover, in the study of Fabella, (2022) he found out that the school administrator's leadership behavior was significantly related to the job satisfaction of teachers.

The indicator, My superior acknowledges my achievements and contribution in the organization obtained the highest mean score of 4.59 (SD=0.65), described as Strongly Agree and interpreted as Very Satisfied. This means that the respondents are pleased with the amount of acknowledgment they receive from their immediate superiors. Principals and administrators play a critical role in boosting teacher job satisfaction through their leadership and recognition practices. In the interview part of this study, respondents honestly answered that they feel that the support from school leaders is very minimal and very hard to get. This implies that there are school administrators who are very hard to please. Results are supported by the study of Bona (2022) when she concluded that teachers value recognition from their superiors as a significant factor in job satisfaction. This includes acknowledgment of their work, achievements and contributions to the school.

Moreover, the indicator, access to the management whenever the superior does not listen got the lowest mean of 3.38 (SD=0.67, described as Neutral and interpreted as Undecided. This means that respondents neither agree nor disagree that they have access to the management. The results suggest that clear communication of roles and access protocols, as well as a culture of shared leadership, could help mitigate any uncertainty. However, what usually happens is that teachers have no direct access to the higher-ups, especially when the school principal is influential. Instead of attending to the problem, teachers are often given an implied concept to just keep quiet and let it go or worse, they are told the statement "wait till you become" as a response to their complaints. This is quite alarming because, according to the study of Fabella (2022), school

administrators' leadership behavior was significantly related to the job satisfaction of teachers. This suggests that effective leadership and supervision can positively impact teacher job satisfaction.

In addition, Spence (2022), said that the value of the teaching job in the community is crucial for their role in society. This value is demonstrated in the teachers' community development, role modeling, and holistic and professional development. Research emphasizes the substantial impact of workplace conditions on teacher satisfaction, highlighting factors such as administrative support, leadership, student behavior, school atmosphere, and teacher autonomy as crucial determinants of job contentment. These findings underscore the importance of creating supportive and positive work environments that foster teacher satisfaction and overall well-being. The research findings of Gomez (2023) revealed that teachers' work environments, particularly role clarity, teamwork, and socio-emotional support, are consistently observed.

Table 10 Distribution of Teachers' Level of Job Satisfaction in terms of Benefits and Rewards

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
There is fair amount of pay for the work I do.	4.11	0.68	Agree
The benefits I receive are satisfying.	4.16	0.68	Agree
Teaching provides me with financial security.	4.20	0.66	Agree
Rewards are given for those who give exemplary work within the organization.	4.12	0.68	Agree
The benefits and rewards offered by my department are competitive compared to other agencies.	4.11	0.72	Agree
The department values and appreciates my contributions as a teacher in terms of benefits and rewards.	4.17	0.65	Agree
The benefits offered by my department adequately meet my needs and expectations.	4.18	0.64	Agree
I am satisfied with the work-life balance that my benefits and rewards allow you to maintain.	4.18	0.69	Agree
I feel satisfied with the retirement and pension plans offered by my department.	4.51	0.69	Strongly Agree
I am satisfied with the health insurance provided by the department.	4.17	0.70	Agree
Overall	4.19	0.68	Agree

Legend:

4.50 – 5.00	Strongly Agree/Very Satisfied	1.50 - 2.49	Disagree/Dissatisfied
3.50 – 4.49	Agree/Satisfied	1.49 below	Strongly Disagree/ Very Dissatisfied
2.50 – 3.49	Neutral/Undecided		

Table 10 shows the distribution of teachers' level of job satisfaction in terms of Benefits and Rewards with an overall mean of 4.19 (SD=0.68) described as Agree and interpreted as Satisfied. This means that rewards and benefits play a significant role in teacher job satisfaction. When teachers feel that their efforts are recognized and rewarded appropriately, it enhances their overall satisfaction and commitment to the profession. Extrinsic rewards like competitive salaries, performance-based bonuses, and benefits like healthcare and retirement plans are important for attracting and retaining

teachers. These tangible rewards provide financial security and stability. However, intrinsic rewards like seeing student growth, making a difference, and opportunities for professional development tend to have a greater impact on long-term teacher satisfaction and motivation.

This result is in conformity with the study of Baluyos et al. (2019), which said and emphasized that job satisfaction is essential for work performance and found that teachers were highly satisfied with their pay, which contributed to their overall job satisfaction.

As observed in the results, the indicator I feel satisfied with the retirement and pension plans offered by my department got the highest mean of 4.51 (SD=0.69), described as Strongly Agree and interpreted as Very Satisfied. This means that teachers agreed on this statement are highly fulfilled with the retirement benefits offered by the Department of Education. Most public school teachers in the Philippines participate in defined benefit retirement plans provided by the Government Service Insurance System (GSIS), which bases benefits on years of service and final salary. According to Gumiran (2022), teachers are confident in their retirement plans and the retirement benefits that they are offered within the department of education. However, teachers may face financial challenges in retirement, but with proper education about financial planning and utilization of available retirement benefits, they can achieve financial stability and enjoy their retirement.

Additionally, the indicator there is fair amount of pay for the work they do got the lowest mean of 4.11 (SD=0.68) described as Agree and interpreted as Satisfied. This means that the respondents get and receive equitable compensation relative to the effort, skill and time invested in their work. According to Rokeman (2023), when teachers receive benefits and rewards tailored to their individual needs and performance, it can enhance their overall job satisfaction and motivation to excel in their roles.

The indicator, the benefits and rewards offered by the department are competitive compared to other agencies, got the same lowest mean of 4.11 (SD=0.72), described as Agree and interpreted as Satisfied. This means that many teachers feel they are underpaid and under compensated for the amount of work they do. For instance, teachers often work far more hours than they are paid for, with some working 70+ hours per week, similar to investment bankers, but at much lower pay rates. There is a growing wage gap between teachers and other college-educated professionals, with teachers now making 17% less on average. Teachers often have to take on additional part-time jobs to make ends meet, which can lead to burnout and lower commitment to teaching. These results are supported by the study of Viray (2022), which indicates that many teachers firmly disagree with the notion that they are fairly paid, citing factors like long work hours, growing wage gaps, and inadequate compensation structures. This dissatisfaction with pay levels is a major source of frustration and a key driver of teacher shortages and turnover.

Table 11 Distribution of Teachers' Level of Job Satisfaction in terms of Recognition

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
The work I do is appreciated.	4.59	0.73	Strongly Agree
My evaluation provides me with meaningful information about my performance.	4.31	0.72	Agree
The department values and acknowledges professional growth and development.	4.53	0.68	Strongly Agree
The feedback and praise I receive from my colleagues and superiors are satisfying.	4.33	0.68	Agree
The opportunities for public recognition, such as awards or honors, provided by our department are satisfying.	4.52	0.68	Strongly Agree
The department provides adequate opportunities for me to showcase my skills and expertise.	4.27	0.70	Agree
The level of support and encouragement I receive from the department in terms of recognition is satisfying.	4.32	0.68	Agree
I receive fair amount of recognition for the work I do.	4.32	0.69	Agree
The department promotes a culture of recognition and appreciation among its staff members	4.39	0.75	Agree
I am satisfied with the overall recognition and appreciation I receive for my work as a teacher.	4.69	0.64	Strongly Agree
Overall	4.43	0.70	Agree

Legend

4.50 – 5.00	Strongly Agree/Very Satisfied	1.50 - 2.49	Disagree/Dissatisfied
3.50 – 4.49	Agree/Satisfied	1.49 below	Strongly Disagree/ Very Dissatisfied
2.50 – 3.49	Neutral/Undecided		

Table 11 shows the distribution of teachers' level of job satisfaction in terms of Recognition with an overall mean score of 4.43 (SD=0.70), described as Agree and interpreted as Satisfied. This means that the respondents have positive responses regarding this aspect. In the interview, a good number of respondents revealed that they are satisfied with their teaching job in terms of responsibility, advancement and recognition for a job well done. When teachers feel their efforts are valued and recognized, it boosts their self-esteem, renews their confidence in their teaching abilities, and validates their ideas and expertise. This is related to the study of Movsessian (2019) which illustrated recognition programs can boost a teacher's morale and validate their perceptions among students, parents, and colleagues. It can also renew confidence in teaching and give teachers a sense of pride and satisfaction in their work.

In the same table, the indicator I am satisfied with the overall recognition and appreciation I receive for my work as a teacher got a mean of 4.69 (SD=0.64), described as Strongly Agree and interpreted as Very Satisfied. Also, it means that the respondents are highly satisfied in this aspect. In the locale of this study, teachers who are performing extraordinarily in whatever aspect of their teaching jobs are being rewarded and recognized during the Gabing Parangal which is a division-wide recognition program. Results confirmed the study of Andrews (2021), which indicated the significance of recognition in boosting teacher morale, motivation and satisfaction. Moreover, teachers responded in the interview part that they are satisfied with the recognition they receive for

a job well done and that recognition can have a profound impact on teachers, making them feel valued and appreciated.

However, the indicator, The department provides adequate opportunities for me to showcase my skills and expertise, obtained the lowest mean score of 4.27 (SD=0.70), described as Agree and interpreted as Satisfied. This indicator is about the limited opportunities offered to teachers for them to showcase their skills. In the locale of the study, there are indeed very limited avenues for teachers to showcase their skills especially in schools with many teachers. In large schools, it is very difficult to ensure that you will be chosen to represent the institution in contests or even train or coach students to join contests. Likewise, in a large school, it is difficult for teachers to have their voices heard and receive personalized feedback on their progress. In addition, the overcrowding of facilities and resources in larger schools can also constrain teachers' ability to utilize specialized spaces like ICT labs for enrichment. This result is similar to the study of Garcia (2019) which highlighted how limited opportunities for collaboration, influence over curriculum and professional development can hinder teachers' ability to share their expertise and shape their own growth.

Furthermore, recognition plays a crucial role in boosting employee morale, increasing loyalty, and fostering a sense of connection to the organization. When employees feel valued and appreciated for their contributions, they are more likely to be engaged, motivated, and committed to their work, leading to higher levels of job satisfaction and performance. Movsessian (2019) also illustrated recognition programs can boost a teacher's morale and validate their perceptions among students, parents, and colleagues. It can also renew confidence in teaching and give teachers a sense of pride and satisfaction in their work.

Table 12 Distribution of Teachers' Level of Job Satisfaction in terms of Communication

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
The level of communication is good within the organization.	3.32	0.65	Neutral
As it plans for the future, my department asks for my ideas.	4.27	0.68	Agree
I have opportunity to give input on decisions affecting my work.	4.27	0.69	Agree
I know how my department measures its success.	4.28	0.65	Agree
The department values and prioritizes effective communication as an essential aspect of teaching and learning.	4.29	0.65	Agree
I am satisfied with the effectiveness of communication tools and technologies used in our organization.	4.27	0.65	Agree
The organization encourages open and transparent communication among all stakeholders.	4.52	0.62	Strongly Agree
I am satisfied with the frequency and quality of communication between me and my students' parents or guardians.	4.29	0.65	Agree
My department provides adequate channels for me to express our opinions and concern.	4.20	0.68	Agree
I often receive timely and relevant information from our department regarding important updates or changes.	4.27	0.66	Agree

Overall		4.20	0.66	Agree
Legend:				
4.50 – 5.00	Strongly Agree/Very Satisfied	1.50 - 2.49	Disagree/Dissatisfied	
3.50 – 4.49	Agree/Satisfied	1.49 below	Strongly Disagree/ Very Dissatisfied	
2.50 – 3.49	Neutral/Undecided			

Table 12 shows the distribution of teachers' level of job satisfaction in terms of Communication with an overall mean of 4.20 (SD=0.66) described as Agree and interpreted as Satisfied. This means that the respondents acknowledged the importance of open communication within the organization in order to achieve teachers' satisfaction. Open and effective communication is widely recognized as critical for the success of educational institutions and the satisfaction of teachers. When communication channels are clear and transparent, it enables teachers to better understand the school's vision, goals, and expectations.

Moreover, open communication fosters a sense of trust, collaboration, and shared ownership over the school's direction. Teacher respondents also recognize that open, transparent, and collaborative communication is essential for creating a positive, productive work environment where they can thrive. Strong communication enables teachers to be more effective, engaged, and committed to their schools. This confirmed the results of the study of Nadeem (2020) which reiterated that effective communication within the school organization can lead to a healthy environment and healthy relations between principals and teachers.

It is clearly evident that the indicator The organization encourages open and transparent communication among all stakeholders obtained the highest mean score of 4.52 (SD=0.62), described as Strongly Agree and interpreted as Satisfied. This means that in terms of being open and transparent in communicating with all stakeholders, the respondents agree and are satisfied with how it is done. This can be related to the strengthening of a School-Based Management system that allows all stakeholders to get involved in the whereabouts of the school. The results of this study conformed with the study of Chiloane (2023). He opined that regular and open communication fosters a culture of accountability by keeping stakeholders informed of progress, achievements, and challenges, promoting a sense of responsibility among team members and stakeholders.

Moreover, the indicator the level of communication is good within the organization described as neutral got the lowest mean of 3.32 (SD=0.65), described as Neutral and interpreted as Undecided. Contextually, there are workplaces that have factions between the members of the teaching staff which might be one of the factors of a not-so-good level of communication within the organization. Accordingly, these factions have become common already in organizations due to individual differences. Divisions or factions among teachers can undermine positive conditions. When teachers are not aligned or working together effectively, it can lead to frustration, resentment, and a dysfunctional work environment.

Indeed, disunity and lack of collaboration among teachers can have significant downsides for schools. Effective leadership and professional supports are keys to promoting a cohesive, productive teaching staff. These results related with the study of Kheswa (2020), which emphasized that when there is a lack of effective communication, it contributes to a deterioration of the culture of learning and teaching because educators feel deprived of opportunities to voice their opinions and concerns. This leads to low morale, conflicts, and job dissatisfaction among teachers.

Similarly, miscommunication is preventing the appropriate flow of information across departments, forcing teachers to repeat their work due to misinformation and work unpaid overtime. As a result, instructors wind up undertaking jobs unrelated to their profession; some of them end up doing more work than others, thus battling with the long working hours connected with this circumstance, and are left in states of loss, hurting their trust in the leadership team (Tannous, 2021).

Table 13 Distribution of Teachers' Level of Job Satisfaction in terms of Coworker Relationship

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
There is an open, honest and respectful communication between co-workers.	4.07	0.69	Agree
Teachers in my school collaborate, share ideas, and support each other's work and projects.	4.04	0.62	Agree
There is effective teamwork and cooperation for a common goal in our school.	4.15	0.70	Agree
I ensure a mutual trust and confidence in each other's abilities and intentions.	4.03	0.66	Agree
There is respect for each other's opinions, contributions and boundaries.	4.10	0.65	Agree
There is understanding and empathy towards colleagues' perspectives, feelings, and challenges.	4.10	0.61	Agree
I help addressing conflicts, disagreements and find mutually acceptable solutions.	4.10	0.62	Agree
I acknowledge and appreciate and appreciate each other's efforts and contributions.	4.15	0.69	Agree
There are positive and friendly interactions, both in professional and informal settings in our school.	4.14	0.70	Agree
I offer and receive support during challenging times, both personally and professionally	4.21	0.66	Agree
Overall	4.11	0.66	Agree

Legend:

4.50 – 5.00	Strongly Agree/Very Satisfied	1.50 - 2.49	Disagree/Dissatisfied
3.50 – 4.49	Agree/Satisfied	1.49 below	Strongly Disagree/ Very Dissatisfied
2.50 – 3.49	Neutral/Undecided		

Table 1 shows the distribution of teachers' level of job satisfaction in terms of Coworker Relationship with an overall mean of 4.11 (SD=.66), described as Agree

and interpreted as Satisfied. This means that the respondents are usually contented and happy with the level of their relationship with their colleagues. Teachers who experience these positive collegial relationships are more likely to feel engaged, motivated, and able to cope with stress. It reduces feelings of isolation and burnout. Collaborative practices like peer mentoring, joint lesson planning, and sharing best practices allow teachers to learn from and support each other, further boosting satisfaction. This is supported by the study of Ares (2022) on the relationship between colleagues and job satisfaction among Filipino teachers, where she found that teachers who have a high level of relationship with colleagues are more likely to be satisfied with their jobs.

As seen in the table, the indicator I offer and receive support during challenging times, both personally and professionally, got the highest mean of 4.21 (SD=0.66), described as Agree and interpreted as Satisfied. This means that respondents agree and that they are content with how they give and receive support from their colleagues. In the interview portion, the researcher found out that teachers' relationship and support with their colleagues influence their job satisfaction levels. This support is a resource for teachers and has a positive influence on their performance. This result is supported by the study of Buonomo (2022). In his study, he concluded that teachers' perceived stress is affected by frequent cooperative activities with colleagues, which can lead to more giving and receiving of support at the workplace.

However, the indicator, I ensure a mutual trust and confidence in each other's abilities and intentions, got the lowest mean of 4.03 (SD=0.66), described as Agree and interpreted as Satisfied. This means that respondents somehow agree to have trust and confidence with their colleagues and that they are satisfied with how they interact with their coworkers on this aspect. Open and transparent communication is essential for building trust between teachers. They need to feel comfortable sharing ideas, concerns, and feedback without fear of judgment. Acknowledging each other's strengths, celebrating successes, and providing constructive feedback help teachers develop confidence in their colleagues' abilities.

Further, teachers need to believe their colleagues have the best interests of students and the school at heart. Demonstrating a shared commitment to the school's mission and values is key. Also, avoiding gossip, undermining behaviors, and protecting each other's reputations nurtures an environment of mutual trust and respect. Research suggests that teachers trust each other more than they trust experts. Within the school, transparent decision-making processes and equitable distribution of workloads can reassure teachers that the school is operating with fairness and integrity. Results confirmed the study of Childress (2019) which said that teachers trust for each other is attributed to the fact that teachers have no choice but to rely on each other due to the lack of support from schools and districts in providing necessary curriculum resources.

Table 14 Summary of Teachers' Level of Job Satisfaction

Variables	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Work and Workplace	4.26	0.72	Satisfied
Supervisor and Management	4.22	0.67	Satisfied
Benefits and Rewards	4.19	0.68	Satisfied
Recognition	4.43	0.70	Satisfied
Communication	4.20	0.66	Satisfied
Co-worker Relationship	4.11	0.66	Satisfied
Overall	4.24	0.68	Satisfied

Legend:

4.50 – 5.00	Strongly Agree/Very Satisfied	1.50 - 2.49	Disagree/Dissatisfied
3.50 – 4.49	Agree/Satisfied	1.49 below	Strongly Disagree/ Very Dissatisfied
2.50 – 3.49	Neutral/Undecided		

Table 14 displays the summary of teachers' level of job satisfaction with an overall mean of 4.24 (SD=0.68), interpreted as Satisfied. Improving overall teacher job satisfaction has been shown to lead to better student outcomes, higher teacher retention rates, and a more positive school environment. It is a key priority for education systems globally. Ensuring high levels of overall job satisfaction among teachers is essential for attracting, developing and retaining talented educators who can deliver quality instruction and support student achievement. Addressing the key drivers of teacher satisfaction should be a top priority. Results contradicted the survey conducted by Merrimack College and the EdWeek Research Center (2022), revealed that only 12% of teachers reported feeling very satisfied with their jobs, marking a significant decline from previous years. Factors contributing to this dissatisfaction include overwork, low pay, lack of respect, and challenging working conditions, leading to a sense of disillusionment among teachers.

Meanwhile, the highest-rated aspect of job satisfaction is recognition with a mean score of 4.43 (SD=0.70), interpreted as Satisfied. This means that there is show of recognition in schools. It includes providing positive feedback on their teaching performance, celebrating teachers' successes and milestones publicly, nominating teachers for awards and honors, empowering teachers to take on leadership roles and fostering a culture of appreciation and respect in the school community. In addition, the respondents opined in the interview that they receive high level of respect and recognition from the general public which boosts their self-esteem thus leading to positive results in terms of teaching and learning.

In a study by Hodges (2024), results show that recognition needs to be individualized and authentic. Ideally, administrators should create what we call a "recognition-rich environment" with praise coming from all directions not just during teachers' day. In addition, consistent recognition for doing good work has a direct influence on the key performance measures that we use to evaluate our schools.

Teachers who receive regular recognition and praise are more productive, engaged at work, and more likely to stay with their school.

On the contrary, the lowest-rated variable of job satisfaction is coworker relationship with a mean score of 4.11 (SD=0.66), interpreted as Satisfied. In this aspect, there is a need to increase this level given the importance of having good relationship among teachers in an institution. By consistently practicing relationship-building behaviors, teachers can strengthen their bonds with coworkers, enhance their overall job satisfaction, and create a more positive, collaborative school environment. These behaviors include fostering open and clear communication, building trust and respect, developing collaborative problem-solving skills, cultivating a spirit of camaraderie and kindness and seeking opportunities to be helpful and forgiving. Strong coworker relationships are a key foundation for teacher well-being and effectiveness. As mentioned in the study of Candra (2023), relationship with colleagues improve mental health by reducing depression, increase job satisfaction essential for encouraging retention, and increase engagement and teamwork.

Research Question 3. Is there a significant relationship between the teachers’ perceived level of core behavioral competency and their job satisfaction?

This research explores the significant relationship between the level of core behavioral competencies and teachers’ job satisfaction. Developing core behavioral competencies like results focus, teamwork, and service orientation leads to better job performance and outcomes. When teachers consistently demonstrate these competencies, they are able to set and achieve ambitious goals, collaborate effectively with colleagues, and provide high-quality support to students. By analyzing the impact of these competencies on job satisfaction, the study seeks to determine how effectively these competencies can help in improving the level of fulfillment of the teachers while they are doing their jobs, leading to better retention and lower turnover.

Table 15 Results of the Test on Relationship between the Core Behavioral Competencies and Teachers’ Job Satisfaction

Core Behavioral Competencies	Teachers’ Job Satisfaction						
	Work and Workplace	Supervisor and Management	Benefits and Rewards	Recognition	Communication	Co-worker Relationship	Overall
	r-value p-value	r-value p-value	r-value p-value	r-value p-value	r-value p-value	r-value p-value	r-value p-value
Self-Management	0.375** 0.002 S	0.259** 0.040 S	0.426** 0.008 S	0.232** 0.003 S	0.324** 0.005 S	0.067 0.135 NS	0.281* 0.032 S

Professionalism and Ethics	0.490**	0.238**	0.169	0.316**	0.112	0.422**	0.291
	0.024	0.031	0.121	0.025	0.789	0.028	0.169
	S	S	NS	S	NS	S	NS
Results Focus	0.070	0.380**	0.142	0.122**	0.374**	0.036	0.254
	0.118	0.041	0.351	0.001	0.037	0.421	0.167
	NS	S	NS	S	S	NS	NS
Teamwork	0.229**	0.002	0.037	0.306**	0.237**	0.461**	0.212
	0.022	0.971	0.404	0.040	0.012	0.023	0.245
	S	NS	NS	S	S	S	NS
Service Orientation	0.269**	0.396**	0.330**	0.403**	0.102	0.059	0.260
	0.020	0.030	0.007	0.040	0.971	0.184	0.209
	S	S	S	S	NS	NS	NS
Innovation	0.110	0.019	0.030	0.312**	0.014	0.141	0.104
	0.827	0.678	0.494	0.009	0.750	0.355	0.519
	NS	NS	NS	S	NS	NS	NS
Overall	0.257	0.216	0.189	0.281	0.194	0.198	0.234
	0.169	0.299	0.230	0.020	0.427	0.191	0.224
	NS	NS	NS	S	NS	NS	NS

Legend: S- Significant

NS-Not Significant

r-values	Description	r-values	Description
0.00-.09	No Linear Relationship (NLR)	0.10-0.49	Weak Positive Relationship (WPR)
0.50-0.69	Moderately Positive Relationship (MPR)	0.70-0.99	Strong Positive Relationship (SPR)
1.00	Perfect Linear Relationship (PLR)		

Table 15 shows the results of the test of relationships among the variables of core behavioral competencies, which revealed that self-management has a significant relationship with job satisfaction. Despite the fact that it has a weak positive relationship with an r-value of 0.281, such is enough to display significance as seen in

its p-value which is .032($p < .05$). This result suggests that this relationship is relevant and meaningful. Self-management skills could potentially enable teachers to better navigate their workload, collaborate effectively, and take advantage of growth opportunities, eventually leading to job satisfaction. This is supported by the results of the study conducted by Raebum (2023) which details the positive significant relationship between self-management and job satisfaction among their employees. The study also highlighted that self-management indicators such as adaptability, initiative and achievement orientation were strongly correlated with job satisfaction.

In self-management, only coworker relationship is not statistically associated with an r-value of .067 ($p = .135$). It is possible that self-management is more closely linked to individual performance and productivity rather than the relational aspects of the workplace. Strong self-management may enable teachers to be effective but not necessarily drive stronger coworker bonds. Professionalism and Ethics, on the other hand, is associated with work and workplace ($r = .490$; $p = .024$), supervisor and management ($r = .238$; $p = .031$), recognition ($r = .316$; $p = .025$) and coworker relationship ($r = .422$; $p = .028$). Additionally, Results-focus is statistically correlated with superior and management ($r = .380$; $p = .041$), recognition ($r = .122$; $p = .001$) and communication ($r = .374$; $p = .037$). Teamwork is also linked with work and workplace ($r = .229$; $p = .022$), recognition ($r = .306$; $p = .040$), communication ($r = .237$; $p = .012$), and co-worker relationship ($r = .461$; $p = .023$). In terms of service orientation, it has a significant positive relationship with work and workplace ($r = .269$; $p = .020$), superior and management ($r = .396$; $p = .030$), benefits and rewards ($r = .330$; $p = .007$), and recognition ($r = .407$; $p = .080$). Finally for innovation, it only has an interconnection with recognition with an r-value of .312 and p-value of .009.

Further, these findings have important implications for teacher retention. They highlight the need to develop the core behavioral competencies of the teachers to ensure that they are fulfilled in their jobs. Feeling empowered, supported by colleagues, and making a positive impact on students all contribute to higher job satisfaction. This in turn leads to better retention and lower turnover.

The r-values of the variables such as recognition and the variables of core behavioral competencies indicate a positive correlation suggesting that recognizing teachers' efforts can help in improving core behavioral competencies. The r-value which is 0.281 ($p = 0.02$) indicates that this correlation is statistically significant, which means that the probability that this result is due to chance is nearly zero. Therefore, the data intensely propose that in general, the level of core behavioral competencies of teachers is associated with job satisfaction level.

The result confirms the same relationship established by previous researchers (Rataj, 2022) on the positive relationship between core behavioral competencies and teachers' job satisfaction. Additionally, Baluyos (2019) suggests that behavioral competencies are strong predictors of job satisfaction. Employees who possess certain behavioral competencies are more likely to be satisfied with their jobs. Hence, in order to ensure that the job satisfaction of the teachers is high, their core behavioral competencies should be considered.

In conclusion, the data from Table 15 provide valuable insights into the relationship between core behavioral competencies and the variables of teachers' job satisfaction. The significant correlations observed in the self-management and job satisfaction variables such as work and workplace, supervisor and management, benefits and rewards, recognition and communication indicate that these aspects of teachers' job satisfaction are strongly influenced the way teachers manage themselves. Specifically, professionalism and ethics positively impact educators' satisfaction in terms of work and workplace, supervisor and management, recognition and co-worker relationships. It is also noticeable that core behavioral competencies have a positive influence on job satisfaction in terms of recognition. These findings suggest that investing in targeted development initiatives on behavioral competencies can lead to tangible improvements in these areas, ultimately enhancing the overall quality of job satisfaction. However, the lack of significant correlations in the innovation component underscores the need for further investigation focused on this area.

Research Question 4. Based on the findings of the study, what Teacher Competency Development Plan can be designed?

Enhancing teachers' core behavioral competencies is critical for improving job performance, satisfaction, school culture, and student outcomes. It requires a multi-pronged approach of training, support, and creating an environment that enables teachers to thrive. Prioritizing teacher competencies should be a key focus for school leaders and districts. To guarantee fulfillment and satisfaction, effective competency development program with combined techniques and activities is needed. In the end, this program supports the development of a culture of a strong school culture and better student outcomes.

A THREE-YEAR TEACHER COMPETENCY DEVELOPMENT PLAN ON CORE BEHAVIORAL SKILLS AND JOB SATISFACTION

Introduction

A three-year teacher competency development plan focusing on core behavioral competencies and job satisfaction is crucial for teacher retention. This plan offers structured and sustained opportunities for teachers to enhance their behavioral skills to achieve job fulfillment. Through targeted core competency development and job satisfaction programs, faculty members can refine their skills in professionalism and, ethics and co-worker relationships.

Throughout this three-year plan, it is crucial to secure support from school administrators, allocate sufficient resources for professional development, continuously monitor progress and adjust the plan as needed and celebrate successes and share best practices across the school community. By grounding the plan's content in the latest education research, providing engaging learning opportunities, and implementing feedback loops for continuous improvement, the plan can effectively address the diverse needs of teachers and enhance their job satisfaction levels. Ultimately, investing in the development of core competencies of educators and prioritizing their well-being and fulfillment through a

comprehensive faculty development plan can foster a culture of innovation, collaboration, and lifelong learning within educational institution.

Rationale

The Teacher Competency Development Plan is crafted in order to address the issues of teacher retention due to job dissatisfaction. Understanding the factors that contribute to teachers’ job satisfaction, the plan aims to elevate and advance the teachers’ skills and competencies in professionalism and ethics and co-worker relationships.

General Objectives

This teacher competency development plan enables the teachers to:

1. equipped with the knowledge, skills, and dispositions that display professionalism and ethics;
2. develop the ability to cultivate collaborative, supportive relationships with colleagues; and
3. cultivate a positive, supportive work environment that empowers teachers, promotes their well-being, and fosters job satisfaction and retention.

Table 16. Matrix of Development Plan

Year 1: Assess and Develop Self-Awareness							
Areas of Concern	Specific Objectives	Strategies/ Activities	Time Frame	Person/s Involved	Source of Fund	Estimated Budget	Expected Outcome
Professionalism and Ethics	*To maintain a professional image: being trustworthy, regularity of attendance and punctuality, good grooming and communication.	*Evaluation of current professional image using a measuring instrument *Gathering feedback from trusted colleagues and mentors about your strengths and	Throughout the academic year.	School head, teachers, administrator and resource speakers	MOOE PTA Fund	₱20,000.00	*Improved professional image; *Updated wardrobe for good grooming; and *Mastery in active listening and being polite in asking clarifying questions.

	<p>*To make personal sacrifices to meet the organization's needs.</p> <p>*To act with a sense of urgency and responsibility</p>	<p>weaknesses.</p> <p>*Develop the sense of urgency among team members by effectively communicating the importance of strategic goals and involving them in the planning process.</p>					<p>*Communicate the strategic vision and its benefits to the team, ensuring that everyone understands the importance of their roles in achieving the goals.</p>
Co-Worker Relationship	<p>*To establish a culture of open communication and trust.</p> <p>*To foster initial connections among co-workers</p>	<p>*Organize monthly team-building activities to encourage interaction and collaboration among colleagues.</p> <p>*Conduct workshops focused on effective communication skills including active listening and constructiv</p>	Throughout the academic year.	School head, teachers, administrator and resource speakers	MOOE PTA Fund	₱20,000.00	<p>Program proposal for Team Building Activities that are regularly scheduled</p> <p>Activity Matrix for workshops focused on effective communication and giving of feedback.</p>

		e feedback. *Implement Peer Recognition Program					
Year 2: Skill Enhancement							
Professionalism and Ethics	*Enhance Skills in ethical decision-making and conflict resolution *Promote a culture of professionalism within the organization.	*Participate in advanced training focusing on ethical decision-making and conflict resolution strategies. *Establish a Mentorship Program *Peer review sessions	Throughout the academic year.	School head, teachers, administrator and resource speakers	MOOE PTA Fund	₱30,000.00	*Establishment of a mentorship program where experienced professionals guide the newer ones in navigating ethical challenges.
Co-worker relationships	To promote collaboration and removes barrier to teamwork and goal accomplishment across the organization. Develop teachers' skills in	Improve teachers' teamwork and collaboration. Provide training on active listening, giving and receiving feedback,	Throughout the academic year.	School head, teachers, administrator and resource speakers	MOOE PTA Fund	₱30,000.00	Establishment of trust and open communication among teachers through regular team-building activities. Implementation of a system for teachers to provide

	effective communication, conflict resolution, and teamwork	and having difficult conversations Facilitate team-building exercises and collaborative planning sessions					constructive feedback to each other and share best practices. Enhanced collective problem-solving and shared ownership of school initiatives
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Year 3: Integration and Sustainability

Professionalism and Ethics	*Integrate ethical practices into everyday operations. *Sustain a commitment to professionalism and ethics.	*Conduct Policy Review to update organizational policies. *Encourage continuous education *Implement recognition programs that reward employees who exemplify ethical behavior and profession	Throughout the academic year.	School head, teachers, administrator and resource speakers	MOOE PTA Fund	₱30,000.00	*Implementation of an Updating Session focusing on present policies in the organization. *Conduct of Recognition programs for teachers.
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		alism in their work.					
Co-worker Relationships	<p>*Integrate relationship-building practices into daily operations.</p> <p>*Create a supportive and inclusive workplace culture.</p>	<p>*Reinforce continuous learning opportunities.</p> <p>*Establish Teacher Resource Groups as platform for teachers to share their interests.</p> <p>*Conduct an annual relationship assessment</p>	Throughout the academic year.	School head, teachers, administrator and resource speakers	MOOE PTA Fund	₱20,000.00	<p>*Establishment Teacher Resource Group</p> <p>*Crafted Program Matrix for the conduct of annual relationship assessment and recognition.</p>

DISCUSSION

Research question 1 highlights the respondents' core behavioral competencies in terms of self-management, professionalism and ethics, results-focus, teamwork, service orientation and innovation. The results reveal that the respondents consistently demonstrate their self-management skills in their teaching jobs specifically in setting personal goals and directions, needs and development. Also, a noteworthy commitment to teaching is evident, with the majority of teachers demonstrating the values and behavior enshrined in the Norms and Conduct and Ethical Standards for public officials and employees (R.A.6713). Moreover, the teaching workforce is found to achieve results with optimal use of time and resources most of the time. Furthermore, in terms of teamwork, the teachers were found to have applied negotiation principles in arriving at win-win agreements, ensuring peace and harmony in the workplace. Also, teachers develop and adopt service improvement programs through simplified procedures that will further enhance service delivery as part of their service orientation. Finally, the majority of teachers express positive responses in promoting a creative climate and inspiring co-workers to develop original ideas or solutions.

Generally, research question 2 outlines the findings on teachers' job satisfaction in areas such as work and workplace, supervisor and management, benefits and rewards, recognition, communication and co-worker relationship. Teachers are contented in their work and workplace, with mean scores ranging from 4.19 to 4.40, all categorized as "Satisfied." In supervisor and management, they feel satisfied in their superior who acknowledges their achievements and contribution in the organization. In benefits and rewards, they feel satisfied with the retirement and pension plans offered by the department. Teachers are also satisfied with the overall recognition and appreciation they receive for their work as a teacher. In communication, teachers are highly satisfied when the organization encourages open and transparent communication among all of its stakeholders. Finally, in terms of co-worker relationships, they are satisfied whenever they offer and receive support during challenging times, both personally and professionally.

Further, in research question 3, the significant relationship between core behavioral competencies and teachers' job satisfaction is tested at 0.01 level. The results highlight that a significant and weak positive relationship exists between core behavioral competencies and teachers' job satisfaction, with an r-value of .281 and a p-value of .032. This indicates that as the self-management improves, there is a corresponding improvement in teachers' job satisfaction. The statistically significant p-value suggests that this relationship is highly unlikely to be due to chance. Therefore, the data strongly support the concept that higher core behavioral competencies would yield a better job satisfaction level.

Conclusions

From the findings and discussions outlined, the following conclusions are drawn:

The core behavioral competencies of teachers within the Division of Valencia City demonstrate commendable goal-setting skills, consistently showcasing the values and behavior based on standards, constantly achieving results efficiently, and guaranteeing the use of negotiation principles in whatever circumstances. Moreover, teachers yield to simplifying procedures to enhance service delivery, promote a creative climate and inspire co-workers to develop original ideas or solutions.

The assessment of teachers' job satisfaction reveals a consistent satisfied response across various areas, which could significantly contribute to elevating teacher retention in the field and fostering a culture of working with fulfillment within educational institutions. However, while they excel in some areas, there is a room to improve the satisfaction levels of teachers in other parts by continuously studying the different factors that warrant a higher level of fulfillment.

The significant relationship observed between core behavioral competencies and teachers' job satisfaction emphasizes the vital part of a high level of core competence in enhancing the teacher's level of fulfillment in his/her job. Therefore, investing in strategies

to reinforce the development of these core behavioral competencies can be contribute in promoting a joyful, contented and fulfilled teaching force whose influence transcends not only inside the classroom but to the whole community.

Recommendations

Based on the relevant findings and conclusions drawn, this study proposed the following recommendations:

1. The Department of Education may implement programs to revisit the standards of professionalism and ethics. Additionally, they could plan support mechanisms and schemes to focus on requiring aspiring teachers to demonstrate proficiency in the professional standards before earning certification as well as providing mentoring and induction support for new teachers to help them develop as professionals.
 2. The teachers could grab opportunities to enhance coworker relationships such as fostering open and clear communication, building trust and respect, cultivate a sense of camaraderie and kindness and seek opportunities to be a mentor to a colleague. These could be achieved through active participation in team building activities and other collaborative endeavors.
 3. The Division of Valencia may facilitate a supportive environment not only for teachers' professional growth but also for teachers' well-being. They may initiate development programs that aim to develop core behavioral skills to promote job fulfillment and eventually address issues on teacher retention.
 4. The schools in the Division of Valencia City may opt to adopt the teacher competency development plan designed in this study in order to ensure that teachers are satisfied across areas of their teaching job. They may use this comprehensive approach to develop the core behavioral competencies that are essential for their job satisfaction, effectiveness, and the overall success of the school.
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Compliance with Ethical Standards

Before starting the study, the researcher submitted the manuscript for ethics review and earned clearance from the office of the Graduate Studies spearheaded by the research coordinator. After which a permit letter to conduct the study signed by the dean was given to the researcher. The proposal was then submitted to the Office of the Schools Division of Valencia City for approval. It was important to emphasize that selected participants and those who chose to participate for any reason participated voluntarily, without any coercion or intimidation. Respondents reserve the right to refrain from answering any questions if they feel uncomfortable.

All respondents received an information letter explaining the purpose, procedures, risks, and benefits of the study and providing the details necessary to make an informed decision to participate. These communications explicitly stated that all information

collected during the study was treated strictly anonymously and no individual names be mentioned. Additionally, respondents were asked to sign a consent form confirming their voluntary participation.

After the study was completed, all respondents had access to the study results. All completed questionnaires were stored securely and access to the data was restricted to researchers and their advisors only. It was very important to emphasize that no physical, emotional, or mental harm can be caused to the participants throughout the research process.

The researcher worked with integrity, which included accurately reporting data and results, avoiding fabrication or falsification, and being transparent about methods and findings.

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